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How Governance Produces Crises: The Dynamics of Alienation on the Eurozone

Yönetişim Krizleri Nasıl Üretiyor: Euro Bölgesinde Yabancılaşma Dinamikleri

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Abstract

Crisis is generally understood as a negative condition, yet it acquires a positive meaning in the context of governance. Especially for political actors, crises can be instrumentalized as strategic moments that enable the reconfiguration of power, the restructuring of bureaucratic and organizational structures, or the justification of extraordinary administrative measures. Although this is vastly studied, it is overlooked that what enables crises to function as a window of opportunity, which becomes possible only when an enabling environment already exists. To discover the inner workings of this process, this paper drawing on Marxist theory argues that the transition from classical public administration to New Public Management and governance has reproduced forms of alienation within the public sphere. Applying the theory onto state as an organization, citizens become parallel subjects of alienation just as workers are alienated from their labor, they have become alienated from public decision-making; when production under capitalism prioritizes capital accumulation, governance prioritizes efficiency, markets, and competition; and where human needs become secondary in capitalist production, the public good becomes subordinate to managerial and neoliberal logics. These forms of alienation generate the conditions in which crises not only emerge but can be effectively instrumentalized by political actors. This paper focuses on the Eurozone Crisis as a case that exemplifies this dynamic of alienation.

Keywords: Governance, Governmentality, Alienation, New Public Management, Eurozone Crisis, Troika

Özet

Genellikle olumsuz bir durum olarak anlaşılan kriz, yönetim bağlamında olumlu bir anlam kazanır. Özellikle siyasi aktörler için krizler, iktidarın yeniden yapılandırılmasını, bürokratik ve örgütsel yapıların yeniden düzenlenmesini veya olağanüstü idari önlemlerin gerekçelendirilmesini sağlayan stratejik anlar olarak araçsallaştırılabilir. Bu konu çokça incelenmiş olsa da, krizlerin bir fırsat penceresi olarak işlev görmesini sağlayan etmenin, ancak elverişli bir ortamın zaten var olması durumunda mümkün olduğu göz ardı edilmektedir. Bu sürecin iç işleyişini keşfetmek için, bu makale Marksist teoriye dayanarak, klasik kamu yönetiminden Yeni Kamu Yönetimi ve yönetişime geçişin kamusal alanda yabancılaşma biçimlerini yeniden ürettiğini savunmaktadır. Bu teoriyi bir örgüt olarak devlete uyguladığımızda,

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vatandaşlar, işçilerin emeklerinden yabancılaştıkları gibi, kamu karar alma süreçlerinden yabancılaşmış paralel özneler haline gelmişlerdir; kapitalizmde üretim sermaye birikimini öncelikli kıldığında, yönetim verimliliği, piyasaları ve rekabeti öncelikli kılar; kapitalist üretimde insan ihtiyaçları ikincil hale geldiğinde, kamu yararı yönetsel ve neoliberal mantığa tabi hale gelir. Bu tür yabancılaşma biçimleri, krizlerin ortaya çıkmasına neden olmakla kalmayıp, siyasi aktörler tarafından etkili bir şekilde araçsallaştırılabilmelerine de zemin hazırlar. Bu makale, yabancılaşma dinamiklerini örnekleyen bir vaka olarak Euro Bölgesi Krizini ele almaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Yönetişim, Yönetimsellik, Yabancılaşma, Yeni Kamu Yönetimi, Euro Bölgesi Krizi, Troika

1. Introduction

Before *crisis* entered the vocabulary of capitalism and became a widely employed concept in political analysis, it denoted a critical juncture in the progression of a disease. This was a crossroads that required a decisive judgment where the patient's life course is dependent on the decision taken, as both action and inaction could alter the trajectory in either a positive or negative direction. Later in the 18th and 19th centuries, crisis as a concept entered political science terminology to describe political and economic upheavals, reflecting a shift from cyclical or linear models of history to one marked by ruptures and critical junctures. Thinkers like Karl Marx, Joseph Schumpeter, and later political economists used the term crisis to analyze capitalism's inherent instabilities, while others, such as Max Weber and Reinhart Koselleck, expanded its use to sociology and historiography.

In capitalism, crises often resulted from contradictions that system created within itself due to overproduction, market saturation, and falling profits. Although Marx evaluated these moments as necessary steps of the system where either exploitation had deepened or society had gotten restructured. He conceptualized the term to analyze systemic contradictions and revolutionary change. Extending his analysis, Marx introduced the concept of alienation to critique social relations that are created by industrial capitalism. He diagnosed alienation as the condition in which workers are severed from control over their labor, the products they create. Hence, they would become estranged to the very labor process that they operate in, and ultimately from their own human potential and from one another. Within this framework, Marx saw crises as decisive moments at which capitalism is forced to confront the symptoms of the very condition it produces. He diagnosed it as alienation. Much like a disease reaching a critical stage, crisis was exposing the system's internal contradictions. This was compelling a determination to either intensify existing relations of exploitation or a structural reconfiguration that may open pathways toward different forms of organization.

This paper draws from the literature that extends this logic beyond labor and production dynamics to the sphere of politics, more specifically governance. A parallel form of alienation occurs when citizens are systematically separated from meaningful control over the political and administrative decisions that shape their lives. Although this separation does not solely reflect a democratic shortfall. Instead, it cultivates the conditions in which systemic crises can erupt and be instrumentalized through governmentality. To illustrate this, the paper argues that the paradigmatic shift from classical public administration to management systematically produces political alienation by weakening citizens' perceptions over public decision-making and diminishing their meaningful avenues for participation. This leads to elevated levels of alienation, generating an enabling environment where the public is more susceptible to actively or passively accepting crisis narratives that frame extraordinary measures as inevitable. Thus, in contexts of high alienation, political actors possess greater latitude to instrumentalize crises. Actors use crises to justify and implement extraordinary administrative or economic measures that would be contested under normal circumstances.

This is visibly shown within the Eurozone, where higher pre-crisis alienation from EU-level technocratic institutions correlated directly with increased public receptivity to the Troika's crisis-framed austerity and reform prescriptions. Yet the public are receptive to such measures but because the public's resistance is neutralized by the perceived lack of institutional power or in other words alienation. The Eurozone Crisis dated between the years 2010-2015 is chosen to apply the theoretical discussion of this paper on the practical world because it constitutes a fitting case to illustrate if the argument holds. As alienation is already embedded within European governance architectures through technocratic European Union (EU) decision-making, the pre-crisis normalization of market-first discourse, and the gradual erosion of national parliamentary autonomy offers unique conditions. In short, this case in question presents us with an opportunity to validate how crises both expose political alienation and condition the measures taken in response, privileging technocratic solutions over democratic choice.

2. The Theoretical Bridge: Applying Marxist Alienation to the State

Alienation as a condition of estrangement or disconnection from oneself, others, or society was introduced into political science primarily through Marxist theory and later sociological and political analyses [1]. When workers become estranged starting from the products of their labor, alienation is possible to trickle down to their relationship to the

world and other people, resulting in feelings of powerlessness, isolation, and meaninglessness. Before Marx's analysis of alienation became foundational for political science, linking economic structures to political and social disconnection W. F. Hegel [2] defined alienation (*Entfremdung*) as an unavoidable phase in human development in his book, *The Phenomenology of Spirit*. According to him, the only thing that is not affected by change is essence. On the other hand, humans as a subject are always in the process of metamorphosis with the effects of time and space. Hegel connects the want of change or the want of defining oneself to *der Geist* (the spirit). Humans, after every determination, negate oneself to determine oneself again in another manner towards universality. Briefly, for Hegel one returns to self what one always had from the beginning without realizing, after consuming the process of alienation. This can be seen in his famous master and slave dialect. At this point it can be said that acknowledging something alien from the point of ego cannot spare that thing from being an alien since it is still positioned oppositely of one's ego.

Subsequent thinkers, Bruno Bauer [3] and Ludwig Feuerbach [4] carried the concept of alienation into religious studies. Their main alienating factor of one to oneself was religion since the idea of an almighty power, in their opinion, was creating a figure with humanlike attributions yet so flawless that cannot be human, causing for people to alienate from their own human acts. Marx radicalized this critique by grounding alienation not in consciousness or belief but in material relations of production. Together with Moses Hess, Marx identified capital and wage labor as the primary sources of alienation, through which individuals become subordinated to economic structures they do not control [5]. Later, social theorists expanded the scope of alienation beyond the workplace. Erich Fromm [6] defended that people alienate themselves from society due to their wants and wishes in capitalist system because the system encourages individuals to relate to themselves and others as commodities. The want of possessiveness and prosperousness makes people see each other and themselves as rivals. This rivalry shapes into being in the pursuit of monetary gain and materials, creeps into the daily lives of people through free time as it essentially created a consumerist middle class. Jean Baudrillard [7], further extended this critique by conceptualizing contemporary society as a *simulacrum*, in which social reality is increasingly mediated by signs, images, and consumption, producing what may be understood as an advanced form of alienation detached from material production altogether.

2.1. Towards a multi-level analysis of alienation

Building on this theoretical tradition, this study conceptualizes alienation as a multi-level phenomenon operating across different levels. At the micro level, where the focus is put on the individual, alienation is revealed as feelings of powerlessness, meaninglessness, and disengagement. At the meso level, where the focus is on society, alienation is social, and it manifests in weakened collective bonds, declining trust among public and fragmented social relations. At the macro level, where the focus is on the (state) organization, political and administrative alienation refers to citizens' estrangement from state institutions and decision-making processes. Together, these dimensions form an enabling environment in which crises can emerge and be effectively instrumentalized. This paper deals with the macro level where alienation is not a feeling, but a structural condition that shows formal disconnection between citizens and governance. Thus, alienation is revealed as loss of control over the product of governance, although citizens bear the consequences without authorship. This erosion of political voice and meaning produces disengagement at scale, proves indicators such as trust data, voter turnout (especially during crisis periods), protest frequency and intensity, and the rise of anti-system/populist parties particularly useful for analyzing macro-level alienation.

Alienation operates at the macro level by (1) restructuring political roles and (2) redefining the very functioning of democracy. On the matter with former, alienation produces an actor-spectator dichotomy in which where decision-making feels inclusive as it is happening transparently in the eyes of the spectator. This dichotomy between actor and spectator is intrinsically linked to the broader shift from government to governance, as this process is well documented in political economy literature. The transition from welfare state understanding to neo-liberal state had fundamentally altered the structural relationship between the state and the citizen. While traditional government relied on hierarchical authority and direct accountability, the governance paradigm, often intertwined with New Public Management (NPM), emphasizes horizontal networks, market-like mechanisms, and efficiency [8]. In this shift, the role of the state transformed from a direct provider of services to a regulator that steers semi-autonomous networks and private actors [9]. As a consequence of this the subject of political sphere goes under a recasting, the citizen ceases to be primarily a constituent with a direct line to sovereign power. Instead, citizens are reimagined as consumers or stakeholders within a complex, fragmented service delivery system. This transition fosters alienation because, while governance mechanisms are rhetorically premised on greater inclusion and participation, in practice they often obscure the locus of actual decision-making power behind a veil of transparency, technical expertise and depoliticized consensus [10].

The "spectator" citizen observes the spectacle of "good governance" that is manifested through benchmarks, transparency reports, and efficiency targets, yet they still remain structurally estranged from the political acts that shape those outcomes. As the state hollows out and delegates authority to non-majoritarian institutions and regulatory bodies, the chain of democratic delegation is stretched, leaving the citizen-spectator to consume the outputs of governance

without possessing the agency to influence its inputs. Thus, the shift to governance reproduces alienation by substituting the political act of ruling with the managerial act of reducing the public to a passive audience of administrative performance rather than active authors of their political reality.

2.2. Alienation as an enabler of the instrumentalization of crises through actor - spectator dichotomy

The dichotomy of actor and spectator began to come into existence at the end of 18th century by the decomposition of the traditional interactive performances. As Sennett [11] notes, the democratization of the performing arts shifted the architecture of performance, focusing attention entirely on the performers rather than the interaction. Over time, the audience ceased to reply, share reactions, or shape the play, transforming into knowledgeable but passive spectators. This dynamic entered the public sphere with the erosion of the division between public and private spaces. Societally, this process is embodied in Michel Foucault's theory of normalization through discourses. The process can be defined as individuals' willing or forceful adaptation to patterns of *regime of truth* [12], where mechanisms of social selection, render individuals unable to adapt to the (creatively) destructive developments of the age. This marginalization and subsequent possible total elimination from the political sphere often create space to actively employ "depoliticization" policies to transform the political individual into even a state of "depoliticized apoliticalism," ensuring that citizens remain estranged from the political process and malleable to power [13]. When this profound disconnection and estrangement from consensus around institutions and norms becomes acute; it creates a vacuum of meaning in the life of *zoon politikon*.

Schnell et al. [14] suggest that because individuals strive for meaningful relations, they will seek "fluid compensation" when their sense of belonging to society is threatened. Their study suggests that the belief in conspiracy theory emerges as an alternative resource to restore this lost meaning. Furthermore, this exclusion breeds a secondary form of alienation described by Olsen [15] as "political discontentment," characterized by "dissatisfaction," "disillusionment," and a sense that the government serves only to specific interest groups rather than the general good of public. Similarly, Dubois [16] argues that political disillusionment is a significant driver of alienation that stems from a perceived lack of progress on critical issues and the "erosion of trust" in political institutions. When citizens perceive political leaders as corrupt or ineffective, social fragmentation and polarization that occurs as a result further detach them from the political system. This creates fracturing, rendering consensus impossible. Furthermore, he adds that erosion of trust is compounded by economic inequality, where public voice is deemed undervalued compared to private interests. Therefore, reinforcing the sense that the actors in power centers are separate from the spectator public who are perceived in periphery.

Thereupon if citizens are relegated to spectatorship, a position where they are estranged from decision-making processes and political influence, political actors can easily instrumentalize their susceptibility or passivity by framing extraordinary administrative measures not as political choices requiring debate, but instead as urgent, expert-driven necessary solutions that fit the grand narrative of survival.

3. Crisis as Window of Opportunity for Creative Destruction

Periods of critical decision-making create junctions in which existing structures are contested. Thus, opportunities arise to reconfigure institutions, policies, or social arrangements. Such moments, while disruptive, can serve as catalysts for the creation of new modes of governmentality. Under the neoliberal paradigm, crises are frequently framed as opportunities for economic correction and reform. This logic has long been disseminated globally through the prescriptions of the Washington Consensus. As David Harvey [17] defines neoliberalization as a process of creative destruction intended to restore class power to economic elites, he links the American transformation toward neoliberalism to the construction of consent. He adds that it is achieved through a strategic alliance of distinct forces that have evolved in two directions. A mobilized conservative voting bloc was an important step in one direction. Their voting behavior surprisingly showed prioritization of cultural and moral issues, revealing that voter behavior isn't always rational towards economic interests. Concurrently, on the other direction, state's role was being redefined to prioritize the security of private property and the integrity of markets over public welfare or social equity. While these processes normalized neoliberal ideology through the capture of cultural and intellectual institutions, these entities promulgated market logic as common sense. Thus, under neoliberalism, instability became rationalized not as a systemic failure but as a structural necessity. In short, this was due to the depiction of government as a burden and market entrepreneurship as freedom. This is a discourse that displaces a collective democratic agency with individualized entrepreneurial autonomy. By doing so it entrenches the hegemony of power centers.

Under neoliberal policies, the government freed itself of its duties toward the public, sustaining its authority instead through mechanisms of security and fear to implement reforms essential for the continuance of capitalism, as it is done most effectively during times of crisis [18]. In a context of crisis, a leader may promise that the conflict will dissolve only if specific policies are executed, manufacturing consent for targeted goals. The public might be more receptive, either actively or passively, to desperate solutions in desperate times. A political passivity might be pointing at political alienation. To understand this phenomenon it is crucial to observe its manifestations; in reduced voter turnout, increasing distrust to government and institutions, and rise in populism. Alienation thus functions as a double-edged

sword. It brings about the crisis by weakening the system and simultaneously enables its technocratic management by stripping the public of agency to prevent resistance. This dynamic forces a critical re-evaluation of the democratic triad: if the market has successfully claimed the monopoly on Liberty, what has become of the system's remaining promises?

3.1. The Triad: Market Liberty, Democratic Equality, and the Deficit of Fraternity

As the literature mainly focuses on how the capitalist economy is creating inequalities, there is an overlooked structural tension within governance that stems from the reconfiguration of the sovereignty triad. The current economic and political system, merged in one, equates Liberty with Capitalism (the Market) while Equality with Democracy. On the surface, these two spheres appear to align. The free market theoretically provides the material opportunities necessary to fulfill democracy's promise of social mobility. Yet as Rousseau argues, true democracy aspires to a condition of "government without government" requiring a self-regulating political community that fuels restlessness [19]. Neoliberalism inverts this and seeks a free market without government with a deregulated economic sphere. While the former aims for collective self-rule, the latter results in unchecked wealth accumulation and social stratification.

This divergence fractures the third promise of the contract: Fraternity. By prioritizing liberty in the sense of *laissez-faire* and equality in the sense of opportunity to upward mobility, the system eviscerates the invisible hand that balances itself through social bonds of solidarity and cohesion that fraternity represents. Consequently, the system leans on the instability it had from the start. Without the stabilizing force of fraternity to mediate between the inequalities of the market and the egalitarianism of the state, crisis becomes inherent to governmentality rather than an accidental anomaly. The state must then manage this inherent instability through the securitization mechanisms as the organic social cohesion required for resilience has been dissolved. At this stage revealing the public not as an active political sovereign, but a passive spectator is critical for understanding the functioning of crises that are starting domestically but becoming international. The triad is important in the way it embodies the idea of sovereignty which constitutes the groundwork of today's international system by placing the nation as the people who are the agents of their own destiny, in other words the agenda setting.

John Kingdon [20] postulates that the agenda setting is determined by two primary factors. Firstly, there are participants who are actors within and outside the government. Secondly, there are processes where the convergence of political, policy, and problem streams are. Within the cogs of the process, public opinion comes forth as a prominent variable. Although modern governance theory depicts decision-making mechanism orbiting around the views of citizens, Kingdon argues that public opinion often functions more as a constraint than a directive force. Consequently, the execution of solicited government policies is contingent upon persuading a potentially restrictive public, which becomes a task that is expedited when crises are utilized as instruments of leverage. A repeated famous remark made by John F. Kennedy in 1950s was clearly stating this perspective that was starting to take shape. "*In the Chinese language, the word crisis is composed of two characters, one representing danger and the other, opportunity*" [21]. While linguistically misleading, as the meaning gets lost in the translation, the statement was politically clear and rhetorically powerful. Crisis as a concept was starting to be and reframed not as a catastrophe, but as a positive phenomenon for restructuring. The relative stability associated with the New Deal order was gradually transitioning into a new governance paradigm following the postwar economic boom. This new manner that was also apparent in Kennedy's speeches was setting the standards of competitiveness of the contemporary governance system by hinting at the ability to manage these crises skillfully by minimizing political risks while maximizing favorable opportunities. Thus, Schumpeter's creative destruction contains the crisis within itself, as the central question for political leaders becomes how to induce the public to accept this destruction of *status quo* with minimal resistance.

Alienation, at this point, arises precisely where the democratic promise of fraternity remains unfulfilled. Banaji et al. [22] offer a critical refinement to this framework by conceptualizing political alienation not as a passive state, but as a conscious cognitive process. In their analysis, Banaji et al. characterize alienation as a distinct from the motivational deficit of apathy. They argue that while the apathetic citizens withdraw because they simply "do not care," the alienated citizen possesses an awareness of the political landscape and consciously refuses to participate in it. This happens due to their perception of the system as non-representative. In the context of the Eurozone crisis, this distinction becomes important because it suggests that the legitimacy vacuum was not caused by a public that failed to understand the technocratic restructuring or a lack of knowledge but by a public that understood it all too well and rationalized their exit as the only logical response to a system where their agency was neglected.

4. The Eurozone Crisis of 2010-2015 as the Exemplary Case

The theoretical framework presented in this paper is better observed when examined through the Eurozone Crisis of 2010-2015, where the political alienation and the instrumentalization of crisis for neoliberal restructuring perfectly crystallizes before, during and in the aftermath of the crisis. This was a multi-year sovereign debt crisis that took place

in the European Union. Several member states of the Eurozone were unable to repay or refinance their government debt or bail out over-indebted banks without the assistance of third-party institutions. These states were most notably Greece, Portugal, Ireland, Spain, and Cyprus and the key actors in question were the third-party institutions that formed a triple ensemble of European Commission (EC), European Central Bank (ECB) and International Monetary Fund (IMF), known as Troika.

Even though the crisis functioned on a sovereign level, the stress and trauma caused provided the precise window of opportunity for Troika to bypass national parliaments and standard democratic procedures. The usual way for a country like Greece to prevent or overcome such crisis would be to devalue its national currency to make exports cheaper and restart growth. Although the countries in the zone shared a single currency, the Euro, and the EU treaties initially had no bailout clause. So, there was no legal framework for "fraternal" financial support between states since they had surrendered their monetary sovereignty. The Eurozone established liberty with free movement of capital in an integrated market and equality within the market through one currency for all but explicitly lacked fraternity. Without fiscal union there was no central treasury to transfer funds from surplus countries like Germany to deficit countries like Greece. When the 2008 global financial crash hit, these capital flows stopped abruptly. Without a fiscal union to absorb the shock, the burden fell entirely on austerity, in which crisis became the only mechanism available to force economic adjustment.

4.1. The Withdrawal: Decline in Voter Turnout

This graph tracks the steady decline in participation in European Parliament elections, reaching its historic low of 42.61% in 2014, precisely at the height of the technocratic restructuring, validating political passivity as a response to unresponsiveness.

Figure 1. Voter Turnout in European Parliament Elections (1999-2024). *Note.* Author's elaboration based on data from the International IDEA Voter Turnout Database (2024)

When the individual data from countries are scrutinized, Greece shows a substantive collapse from a high of 81% in 1981 to just 41% in 2024. The sharp decline post-2009 correlates with the imposition of technocratic austerity measures, illustrating the withdrawal of a populace that feels its vote no longer influences policy. Portugal remains consistently alienated with turnout crashing to the 30-36% range, the lowest among the analyzed group, reflecting deep-seated structural passivity. In contrast, the core nation, Germany shows steady increase in participation, suggesting that the crisis did not alienate voters in the creditor nations to the same extent, as they retained a sense of agency.

Figure 2. Voter Turnout in European Parliament Elections by Country (1979-2024). *Note.* Author’s elaboration based on data from the International IDEA Voter Turnout Database (2024)

4.2. The Crisis of Legitimacy: Trust in the EU

Trust in the European Union plummeted from a high of 52% in 2007 to 31% in 2013, showing the crisis low. This drastic drop quantifies the fracture in consensus via trust when the state prioritized the liberty as market integrity over a fraternal understanding that comes with social welfare; the public consciously withdrew its consent.

Figure 3. Trust in the European Union (2007–2024) *Note.* Data retrieved from Standard Eurobarometer surveys 67–92, European Commission (2024)

Pre-crisis conditions of 2007 show converged trust levels among Greece and Spain, where their levels of trust in the ECB were similar to Germany. The above 50% threshold for all shows that the system was viewed as a shared benefit. Yet a massive divergence is observed with the introduction of Troika interventions during the year of 2010, on Figure 4, this zone of intervention is highlighted in grey. In Germany trust levels slightly drops but remains robust as the ECB acts to protect the stability of currency. On contrary trust drastically dips below 20% in Greece and Spain.

Figure 4. Trust in the European Central Bank (2007–2015). *Note.* Author's elaboration based on data from Eurobarometer and Pew Research Center Global Attitudes Project (2013).

Core European powers portrayed the Greek Referendum in 2015 as an existential choice between staying in the eurozone versus risking exit, not just a vote on specific bailout terms or austerity conditions [26]. This framing within the Crisis discourse supports the data and theory because it exploits political alienation by collapsing democratic alternatives into catastrophic outcomes, enabling elites to bypass deliberation and consolidate technocratic authority.

4.2. The Reaction: Rise of Populism

As a result of the alienation, collective sought a new meaning that they found in populist promises as data reveals that the vote share for populist parties more than doubled from 11% in 2008 to nearly 27% in 2018. This confirms that alienation functions dialectically. It is not just a withdrawal, but a motivation for new, often destabilizing, forms of agency that settles in via crises.

Figure 5. Combined Vote Share of Populist Parties (1998–2018) *Note.* Adapted from the Timbro Authoritarian Populism Index (2019)

The data suggests that citizens felt the system was unresponsive, so they stopped participating. In turn, creating a legitimacy vacuum. And where the public left the room, technocrats entered to implement restructuring measures.

5. Conclusion

Consequently, the system cannot deliver the full democratic promise because it is designed to view fraternity as a friction to market efficiency and equality as a constraint on technocratic governance. This leaves market liberty as the sole surviving value, creating a lopsided structure that is inherently unstable and must rely on the securitization frameworks and permanent crisis management to survive. This study argues that the tension of contemporary governmentality arises from the structural foundation of the systemic triad. The alignment of Liberty with the Market and Equality with Democracy puts forth a dual promise that theoretically offers boundless opportunity and social mobility. Yet in practice inherently restricts or overlooks the third necessary element that is Fraternity. By prioritizing individual competition and race to the top over social solidarity, the system severs the organic bonds of the community, producing a deep and structural alienation.

Alienation operates on different levels with differing units of analysis. Following the ascending order from micro to macro; it takes individual, society and organizations into account. This paper adopted the macro level unit of analysis by focusing on national and supranational organizations and argued that alienation is not merely a passive byproduct. In the absence of fraternal constraints, actors in the power centers are free to concentrate resources by using structural inconsistencies that are prone to instability. Thus, positioning crises as necessary mechanisms to mend the system. The Eurozone case study is used to demonstrate that the theory is validated in the practical world. The crisis was instrumentalized to restructure the state in favor of these power centers, utilizing the very alienation of the public to bypass resistance.

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